

doi:10.5281/zenodo.20266971

Assessment Of Igbo-Ukwu Archaeological Site And Its Significance In Art History Of Nigeria

Ugwu, Isreal Chukwudi¹, Nwaoha chimaroke Chizoba² & Okechukwu, Ifeoma P³.

^{1,2}Department of History and Diplomatic Studies,
Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri, Nigeria

³Department of Music,
Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri, Nigeria

²Corresponding Author: Nwaoha Chimaroke, nwaohachima6@gmail.com 07035567526.

ABSTRACT

The paper assesses Igbo-Ukwu archaeological site and its significance in art history of Nigeria. Archaeological site and material constitute a unique class of non-renewable resources. Through archaeological excavation many artifacts of historical importance have been uncovered at Igbo-ukwu archaeological site. Igbo ukwu is a famous archaeological site and centre for the development of sophisticated casting tradition in bronze objects. The constituent of this culture such as bronze and terracotta have provided a sources of international reputation for Nigeria. The artistic exploit of this culture has continued to generate more tourist interest. The findings reveal that apart from the historical importance and tourist potential, the remarkable style shows the artistic ability and inventiveness of their makers. The use of functional and structural theories guides the study. Primary and secondary sources of data were used in this study.

Keywords: Assessment, Igbo Ukwu, Archaeological Site, Culture, Art History.

INTRODUCTION

Igbo-ukwu in Nigeria is a famous and outstanding centre for the development of sophisticated casting tradition in bronze. Apart from its historical significance and tourism potential, the remarkable style of these objects reveal the artistic ingenuity, ability and inventiveness of their makers (Okpoko and Okpoko, 2002:58).

Igbo ukwu excavation unveil a vast artistic tradition of the people relating to ritual, complex religions system, economy based on agriculture and trade with other African people as far as Nile valley, architectural embellishment associated to the historical art centre in Nigeria. According to Hirst (2018) Igbo ukwu is an Africa iron age archaeological site located near the modern town of Onitsha in Anambra State in the forest zone of Southeastern Nigeria. Igbo Ukwu is a site complex where some bronze and pottery of high artistic value were accidentally recovered from the ground by a man called Isaiah Anozie when digging a cistern in his new compound. The site was scientifically excavated by Professor Thurstan Shaw and other archaeologists between 1959 and 1960 (Ogundele 2014).

Igbo ukwu is notable for three archaeological sites associated with the Nri-Igbo (Shaw, 1975). These sites include Igbo Isaiah (a shrine) Igbo Richard (a burial chamber) and Igbo Jonah (cache).

Sultion (2001) argues that the glass beads recovered at Igbo ukwu might have been manufactured in fustat (old Cairo) and the carnelian might have come from Egyptian and Sahara sources. A study and isotopic analysis of

the beads carried out by Garlake (2002) reveals that the sources of the Igbo ukwu beads metals was of local origin and radio carbon dating has confirmed a 9th century date long before the existing contact with Europe. It is pertinent to note that artifacts such as pottery, bronze, copper and so on discovered at Igbo ukwu have yielded first class ancient cultural remains that now form a significant part of the heritage of Nigeria and African as a whole (Shaw, 1970, Robert Shaw, 1990, Anozie, 1979, Ogundele 2014).

Igbo ukwu people are known for their unique creativity as shown in the photo-evidence of Shaw archaeological excavation, (Shaw, 1970). Onwejeogwu and Onwejeogwu (1976) noted that the quality, quantity and general characteristics of Igbo ukwu artifacts suggest a people with well-organized and complex society.

Statement of the Problem

Igbo ukwu culture has numerous rich and complex hybrid motif and range of symbolism. This was based on the evidences in the discovery of Thurstan Shaw of 1959 and 1960 excavation which unveiled a vast artistic tradition of Igbo ukwu people associated to their historic arts.

The fact that archaeological sites and material constitute a unique class of non-renewable resources and development that have taken place around the areas, it becomes very imperative for this assessment.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to assess Igbo ukwu archaeological site and its significance in art history of Nigeria.

Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Find out the sources of origin of this cultural tradition.
2. Find out what constitute Igbo ukwu archaeological sites and culture
3. To ascertain the vast artistic tradition of Igbo ukwu people

Significance of the Study

The study will be of great benefit to the ministry of culture and tourism as it will serve as guide for the adoption of better policies that will help promote Nigeria cultural heritage and in the long run boast socio-economic development of Nigeria.

It will serve as a reference point to scholars of history and other linking disciplines like sociology, archaeology and anthropology who would like to embark on any research on Igbo ukwu culture.

It will help the indigenes, and non-indigenes of Igbo ukwu people of Nigeria and Africa as a whole to gain knowledge and insight into their art history and heritage.

Methodology

The study was based on observation; interview and focused group discussion were the data gathering technique. Books, academic journal, unpublished thesis, and public library were relied upon for secondary data so as to complement data derived from primary sources.

Conceptual Clarification of Archaeology, Archaeological Site and Culture

There are different definitions of archaeology and each has his own view of the field that reflects his approach, training, abilities and interest. Archaeology is an interpretative practice, an active intervention engaging a critical process of theoretical labour relating to past and present.

Ogundele (2014) defines archaeology as the systematic or scientific study of the past of man within the framework of environment. This is done through the lens of material remains of the behaviours of settlers of a region or site. From these material expressions of the past cultures, archaeologist can peep into the non-material/non tangible dimension of the maker users' lifeway which include religion, kinship and cosmology (Ogundele, 2014). Shaw (1970) in Dada and Orié (2014) refer to archaeology as scientific techniques of digging up the remains of the people of ancient times and study of them to gain knowledge of past event and to reconstruct the way a people lived.

Andah and Okpoko (1994) sees archaeology as a process of retrieving material remain of past human activities through excavation. These definitions clearly indicate and emphasis that archaeology is the study of cultural norms as formulated and perceived by people through the material remains. The use made by people of their past for accessing, and shaping the direction of their future by determining what is worth preserving, what should be conserved and developed, a discipline which constitutes the basis for meaningful communication between human.

However, the use of the term “site” to refer to location where artifacts, human remains and architecture have been found is as old as the discipline of archaeology itself (McCoy, 2020). According to Ogundele (2014) it is difficult to define a site in a concise manner because archaeology is currently experiencing an overhand of concepts, methods and goals. This is because we are in a more competitive world of modern education and development. In view of the above Ogundele (2014:42) defines site as any location or terrestrial space (whether small or large) having traces or evidence of human occupation and/or activities. Dada and Orie (2014:41) also defined site as any place large or small where there are to be found traces of ancient occupations or activities. The usual clue to a site is the presence of artifacts. Examples of major archaeological site found in Nigeria include Nok, Igbo ukwu, Benin and so on. McCoy (2020) sees site as necessary in the generation of primary data, inventories of finds and for linking laboratory result like radio carbon dates to relevant location. However from these definitions, Igbo ukwu is an archaeological site where traces of human occupation and activities were found in the past and radio carbon 14 dating place the site at 9th century.

An archaeological site is a place or group of physical site in which evidence of past activity is preserved either (pre-historical or historic or contemporary) and which have been investigated using the discipline of archaeology (Andah and Okpoko, 1994).

Traditionally, sites are differentiated by the presence of both artifacts and features. Common features are the remains of hearths and houses, Ecofacts, biological materials such as bone, that are the result of human activities but not purposely modified are common at many archaeological sites.

Culture

The concept culture has been variously defined by many professionals. Taylor (in Igwe 2010) defines culture as that complex whole which include knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, custom, values and any other capabilities and habit acquired by man as a member of the society. From the above definition Igwe (2010) sees culture as the whole sum of customs and traditions expressed through society norms, value and beliefs. It is transmitted from generation to generation, culture can be said to have three levels, tangible, value and assumption. Tangible aspect can be seen, touched and felt, value – the beliefs, taboos, ethics and rules, assumptions-perception of reality which may be true or false. It implies that societies did not have discrete culture, but a greater or less share in the degree of general culture so far created and developed by man.

Sida (1997) also defines culture in a broad term to include various aspect of the way of life in a given society example ethics, human rights, gender roles, status of minority groups, religious and language issue.

In view of the above definitions, culture is a sustained pattern of behaviour of Igbo ukwu people, the creative expression of their way of life which embraces such aspect of the social structure as the arts and craft, religion, kingship, the social value system of the people.

Significance of Igbo-Ukwu in Art History of Nigeria

Igbo-ukwu is a famous archaeological site and centre for the development of sophisticated casting traditions in bronze. The artistic exploit according to Andah (1988) in Okpoko and Okpoko (2002) continue to generate tourist interest. The Igbo ukwu objects in bronze and terracotta have provided sources of international reputation for Nigeria. The artistic style shows the creative ability of Igbo ukwu people.

Igbo ukwu bronze amazes the world with a very high level of technical and artistic proficiency and sophistication more advanced than contemporary bronze casting found in Europe (Honour and Fleming 2005). Garlake (2002) compares Igbo-ukwu bronze to the finest jewelry of Rococo Faberge type virtuosity. Willet (1983) observes that the Igbo-ukwu bronzes portray a standard that is comparable to that established by Benvenuto Cellini five hundred years later in Europe in which they called them an exquisite explosion without antecedent or issue. One of the object found: a water pot set in a mesh of stimulated role. Honour and Fleming (2005) describe it as a virtuoso feat of cire perdue (lost wax) casting, its elegant design and refined details are matched by a level of technical accomplishment that is notably advanced than European bronze casting of this period.

Garlake (2002) argues that the high technical proficient and lack of known prototypes of the Igbo-ukwu bronze led to initial speculation in the academic communities that they must have been created after European contact and phantom voyage. Research and isotope analysis have established that the sources of the Igbo ukwu metal is of local origin and radio carbon dating has confirmed 9th century date long before the earlier contact with Europe. The Igbo-ukwu artifacts did away with the hitherto existing colonial era opinions in archaeological

circle that such magnificent work of art and technical proficiency only originate in the area with contact to Europe and could not be created in an acephalous or egalitarian society like the Igbo (Garlake, 2002).

However, some of the glass carnelian beads have been found to be produced in old Cairo at the workshops of Fustat establishing that a long distance trade system extending from Igbo-ukwu to Byzantine era Egypt existed (Chikwendu, et al. 1989, Insoll and Shaw, 1997, Sulton, 2001).

Field (1940) argues again that the Awka people are known to have done a little metal casting. It is practically certain that they (Igbo) never reached the degree of skill required to fashion any of the objects. The Igbo people are not themselves metal worker.

The subsequent research was to prove Field (1940) wrong as twenty years later in 1959/1960 and 1974 Thurstan Shaw and excavation team, excavated three sites around the original find for the Nigeria department of antiquity and later for the University of Ibadan. The archeological digs revealed hundreds of copper and bronze ritual vessels as well as iron swords, iron spear heads, iron razors and other artifacts dated a millennium earlier.

Plate i: Cast Bronze Vessel with animal motif

Plate ii: Bronze Pot

Plate iii: Bronze Bowl Pot

Plate iv: Intricate Bronze Ceremonial Pot

Sample of Bronze from Igbo Ukwu

History of Igbo-Ukwu

Igbo-Ukwu is a town in Anambra State Southeastern Nigeria. The town comprises three quarters, these include Obiuno, Ihite, and Ngo with several villages within each quarter and thirty six (36) administrative wards.

According to Apley (2008) the inhabitants of Igbo-Ukwu had a metal working art that flourished as early as the 9th century. Ogundele (2014) also notes that Igbo-Ukwu is about 40km South-East of Onitsha in Anambra State of Nigeria. The people of Igbo-Ukwu originally known as Igbo-Nkwo ancestors of the present day Igbo as earliest smither of copper and its alloys in West Africa, working the metal through hammering, bending, and twisting. They employ the lost wax technique in the production of bronze sculpture (Apley, 2008).

The ancient site of Igbo-Ukwu is situated in the modern day homelands of Igbo people of Southeastern Nigeria. The site was first discovered by Igbo farmer Isaiah Anozie when he was digging a cistern in his compound, accidentally recovered several bronze objects in 1939. It was not until 1959 that the archaeologist Thurstan Shaw excavated the site (Shaw, 1970).

Geographically, the Igbo-Ukwu is situated in Aguata Anambra State-Nigeria, its geographical coordinate are 6° 1' 0" North 7° 1' 0" East and its original name (with diacritics) is Igbo-Ukwu.

Figure 1: Map of Igbo Ukwu

Source: <https://www.google.com/search?q=map+of+igbo+ukwu+in+Anambra+State>

Theoretical Framework

Theory is a set of idea that provides explanation for something (Okeibunor and Anugwom, 2006). Kerlinger (1973) sees theory as a set of inter-related constructs (concept) definition and propositions that present a systematic view of phenomena by specifying relation among variable with the purpose of explaining and predicting the phenomena. The researcher's view based on scholars, approach to theory is the technique that guides the interpretation of cultural material and record of the past population as it relates to present.

However, no research can be conducted without an underlying theory and model. Theories therefore, guide the selection of research problems, the collection of archaeological data as well as the analysis and interpretation made about culture and history of a people being studied. In high level theories, human

behavioral dynamic are analyzed and interpreted within broad explanatory framework such as evolutionism. (Darwinism) diffusionism, (Hamatic explanation) functionalism, structuralism and Marxism (Ogundele, 2006).

The Researcher uses Structuralism and Functuralism theories which are more relevant to the research work. However; research carried out by scholars at different times and location show the centrality of the application of the middle range theories to archaeological questions and issues (Ogundele, 2006).

Structural Theory

Structure is the way things are done. Individual items and institutions are explained as the result of adaptive expedience. Hodder (1992) submits that; "Structuralism approaches in archaeology could fit with processual archaeology structuralism provides a method and a theory for the analysis of material culture".

Structure as applied in archaeology like the Igbo ukwu archaeological site for example refers to lands, tribes, chiefdom states as well as to reciprocate, redistribute and/prestige transaction which is observed in social and settlement pattern where the visible differentiation in associations and forms is seen as reflecting roles and activities organized in relations to each other. The structure of social relation as a whole is organized so as to allow adaptation to such factor as distribution of environmental resources (uniform or localized), the availability of prestige, its relationship with neighboring social group (Hodder, 1992).

Functional Theory

Culture in functional context is an information system where the message is accumulated, survival information. In this way material culture is functioning at the interface between human organism and the social and physical environment in order to allow adaptation, it has a utilitarian function. (Hodder, 1992)

This view shows that cultural remains are seen as reflecting part of human society and what people do. Material culture is seen as a passive object of cultural use, a mere epiphenomenon of real life; in archaeology and history this applies as much to refuse distribution and the economy as it does to burial, pot decoration and art (Clarke, 1968).

Functional archaeology laid emphasis on cultural context, because of hypothetic deductive nature of explanation. It became important to identify rules of behavior and artifact deposition which were used, the identification of subsystem for example; exchange, subsistence, settlement, refuse disposal and burial, since the role of culture and historical functions were examined.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings reveal that Igbo-Ukwu is symbolized in its bronze work; it was discovered by Thurstan Shaw. Igbo-Ukwu represents archaeological findings discovered in 1960 which justified the richness of Igbo culture. The archaeology of Igbo-ukwu reveals bronze artifacts dated 9th century AD which was initially discovered by Isaiah Anozie in 1939 while digging a well in his compound in Igbo ukwu an Igbo town in Anambra State Nigeria. Three archaeological sites were excavated in 1959 and 1964 by Thurstan Shaw and his team which reveal more than 700 high quality artifacts of bronze and iron as well as about 165000 glasses Carnelians and stone beads, pottery, textiles and ivory.

They are the oldest bronze artifact known in West Africa and were manufactured centuries before the emergence of other known bronze producing centre such as those of Ife and Benin. The bronzes include numerous ritual vessels pendants, crown breast plates, staff ornaments, sword, and fly whisk. The findings also reveal that the ancestor of the modern Igbo-ukwu (Ibo) had as early as 9th century a sophisticated society with surplus of wealth supporting considerable craft specialization including highly developed bronze art with distinctive style of its own.

Igbo ukwu excavation unveil a vast artistic tradition of the people relating to ritual, complex religions system, economy based on agriculture and trade with other African people as far as Nile valley, architectural embellishment associated to the historical art centre in Nigeria.

The state of Igbo ukwu archaeological site before the discovery by Isaiah Anozie in 1939 and Thurstan Shaw excavation in 1959/1960 indicate objects lying in-situ, in which field (1940) argues that the area

was known to have done little on metal casting. It is practically that the Igbo never reached the degree of skill required to fashion any of the objects.

The discovery of Isaiah Anozie and Thurstan Shaw excavation has demonstrate evidence of artistic creativity and ingenuity of Igbo Ukwu people in bronze technology. We can see that Igbo ukwu culture throughout the world has thrown more light on Igbo art history thereby showing that Igbo like other ethnic group in Nigeria has rich cultural heritage. The state of the sites after excavation is the development around the area, many houses have been built, that one can hardly recognize Igbo ukwu archaeological site.

This calls for Site Catchment Analysis (SCA) in which many communities where Igbo ukwu metal working are found in Anambra State and forest region of Nigeria need to be sampled which will lead to further excavation through opening of trenches in selected part of undisturbed forest region in search for the clue for more understanding of Igbo-ukwu artifacts and culture.

In assessing Igbo ukwu archaeological site, the state and condition of the site before, during and after excavation was archaeological remains that explain the relevance of Igbo cultural heritage. Development has taken place around the sites, many of these objects are now found in national museums in Nigeria and department of Art and cultural studies at various Universities in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

The relevance of Igbo-Ukwu archaeological site cannot be overemphasized. The archaeological excavation at the site unveil the vast artistic tradition of Igbo ukwu people which relate to their ritual, complex religious system as well as organized society.

Igbo-ukwu is a famous centre for the development of sophisticated casting traditions in bronze. The objects have yielded a first class cultural remain that form put of Nigeria cultural heritage. The advertisement of these objects internationally shows their uniqueness.

REFERENCES

- Andah, B.W. & Okpoko, A.I. (1994). *Practicing Archaeology in Africa*. Ibadan Wisdom Publisher Ltd.
- Anozie, F.N. (1979). Early Iron Technology in Igboland: Lejja and Umundu. *West African Journal of Archaeology*. Vol. 9
- Apley, A. (2001). Igbo-Ukwu (a 9th century) <http://www.metmuseum.org/toah/hd/igbo/hd/igbo.htm>
Hellbrum Timeline of Art History Metropolitan Museum of Art.
- Chikwendu, V.E., Craddock, P.T., Favourhar, R.M., Shaw, T. & Umeji, A.O. (1989). Nigeria Sources of Copper, Lead and Tin for the Igbo-Ukwu Bronze Archaenotery. 31(11): 29-36 doi/0.1111/j/1475
- Clarke, D.L. (1968). *Analytical Archaeology* London Meltuen.
- Dada, J.P. & Orié, T. I. (2014). *Studies in Environmental Archaeology Owerri* Standard Nigeria publisher.
- Field, J.O. (1940). Bronze Casting found at Igbo Southern Nigeria. Mon XL 1-6 Cross Ref. Google Scholar
- Garlake, P. (2002). *Early Art and Architecture of Africa*. <https://archive.org/details/earlyarchitecture/00gatll/page/120> Oxford University Press.
- Hirst, K.K. (2018). <https://www.thoughtco.com/Igbo-ukwunigeria-site-171378>
- Hodder, J. (1992). *Theory and practice in Archaeology*. London New York, Rutledge.
- Honour, H. & Fleming, J. (2005). *A World History of Arts* (7th ed.) London Laurence King
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Archaeology_of_Igbo-Ukwu
- <https://www.google.com/search?q=map+of+igbo+ukwu+in+Anambra+State>
- Igwe, S. (2010). *How Africa Underdevelopment Africa* Port-Harcourt. Port Harcourt Professional Printer
- Insol, T. & Shaw, T. (1997). Gao and Igbo-Ukwu Beads Inter regional trade and beyond Africa
Archaeological Review.
- Kerlinger, F.N. (1973). *Foundation of Behavioural Research*. New York Holt Rinehart and Winston.
- McCoy, M.D. (2020). The Site Problem: A critical Review of the Site Concept in Archaeology in the Digital Age. *Journal of Field Archaeology* 45: Supl, 10. 1080/00934690.1713283

- Ogundele, S.O. (2004). Rethinking West Africa Archaeology, Ibadan John Archers Publishers Ltd.
- Ogundele, S.O. (2006). Conceptualizing Archaeology and Tourism in Nigeria in issues in Tourism Planning and Development Okpoko P.U. (ed) Nsukka Afro Orbis Publication.
- Ogundele, S.O. (2006). Toward an understanding of the dynamics of sustainable Development in Nigeria. *European Journal of Scientific Research* Vol. 13 No. 3
- Ogundele, S.O. (2014). Understanding Contemporary Archaeology Ibadan John Archers Publisher Ltd.
- Okeibunor, J.C. & Anugwom, E.E. (2006). Sociological Theory: An Insight into Dominant view point, Nsukka Great Ab Express Publisher Ltd.
- Okpoko, A.I. & Okpoko, P.U. (2002). Tourism in Nigeria Nsukka Afro Orbis Publication Ltd.
- Onwejeogwu, M.A. & Onwuejeogwu, B.O. (1976). The search for Missing Link in Dating and Interpreting the Igbo-Ukwu Finds Paideuma 23: 169-188.
- Redman, C.L. (1973). Research and Theory in Current Archaeology: An Introduction in Redman CL (ed.) Research and Theory in current Archaeology. London New York.
- Robert Shaw C. (1990). A History of African Archaeology London Heinemann
- Shaw, T. (1970). Igbo-Ukwu : An Account of Archaeological Discoveries in Eastern Nigeria. Vol. 18:4 London Faber and Faber
- Shaw, T. (1975). The way Archaeology makes entirely new discoveries about the past in Discovery Nigeria's past T. Shaw (ed) Oxford University Press.
- Sida, T. (1997). Development Co-operation in the 21st Century Project Stockholm: Swedish Swedish International Development Co-operation Agency.
- Sulton, J.E. (2001). Igbo-Ukwu and the Nile. *African Archaeological Review*. 18(1): 49-62. Doi 10.1023/A:1006792806737. <https://doi.org/10:1023%2fA%3A100679280806737>)
- Willett, F. (1983). Who taught the Smith of Igbo-Ukwu? <http://www.mozambiquehistory.net/arts/artes/plasticas.19830414smithofIgbo-ukwupdf> New Scientist